

WIND GUST PARAMETERIZATION EVALUATION REPORT

National Observatory of Athens

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FLAME is a research project carried out at the Institute for Environmental Research and Sustainable Development (IERSD) of the National Observatory of Athens (NOA). The overarching goal of the project is the study and characterization of the environmental conditions that promote extreme wildfires in Greece, intending to increase awareness and enhance the preparedness of fire operatives and the public.

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1. Introduction

This report documents information related to **assessing the impact of the developed wind gust parameterization (D4.1) on fire spread prediction**.

Section 2 of this report introduces the numerical experiments conducted with the coupled fire-atmosphere WRF-SFIRE modeling system. Results are presented in Section 3.

2. Numerical experiments

To assess the impact of the developed wind gust parameterization (D4.1) on fire spread prediction, we selected an extreme wildfire event, namely the deadly 2018 Mati wildfire. This event was driven by very strong westerly winds, gusting up to more than 25 m s^{-1} . Hence, it presents an ideal case study for evaluating whether the inclusion of wind gusts in a coupled fire-atmosphere model can fire spread prediction.

We conducted numerical simulations with the WRF-SFIRE coupled fire-atmosphere modeling system, version W4.4-S0.1¹. We configured the model to run on three telescopically nested domains with horizontal grid spacings of 24.5 km (DO1; mesh size of 120×120), 3.5 km (DO2; mesh size of 120×120), and 500 m (DO3; mesh size of 120×150). In the vertical, 41 unevenly spaced, hybrid, terrain-following sigma-pressure levels were defined, with the model top set to 50 hPa. The default terrestrial datasets distributed with the WRF model² were used for the representation of land use, topography, and soil type. Shortwave and longwave radiation processes were parameterized with the RRTMG (Rapid Radiative Transfer Model) scheme³, and the Thompson parameterization⁴ was used for handling microphysics. The Yonsei University Scheme (YSU)⁵ was used to represent the planetary boundary layer, coupled with the revised MM5 scheme⁶ for the parameterization of surface-layer processes. Land-surface processes were

¹ Mandel, J. et al. (2011) Coupled atmosphere-wildland fire modeling with WRF 3.3 and SFIRE. *Geoscientific Model Development* 4, 591-610.

² Skamarock, W.C. et al. (2008) A Description of the Advanced Research WRF Version 3. NCAR Technical Note NCAR/TN-475+STR.

³ Iacono, M.J. et al. (2008) Radiative forcing by long-lived greenhouse gases: Calculations with the AER radiative transfer models. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, D13103.

⁴ Thompson, G. et al. (2008) Explicit forecasts of winter precipitation using an improved bulk microphysics scheme. Part II: Implementation of a new snow parameterization. *Monthly Weather Review* 136, 5095-5115.

⁵ Hong, S.Y. et al. (2006) A new vertical diffusion package with an explicit treatment of entrainment processes. *Monthly Weather Review* 134, 2318-2341.

⁶ Jimenez, P.A. et al. (2012) A revised scheme for the WRF surface layer formulation. *Monthly Weather Review* 140, 898-919.

parameterized with the Unified Noah land surface model⁷, while convective processes were represented with the Grell-Freitas ensemble scheme⁸ in DO1 and DO2 and explicitly resolved in DO3.

The simulation of the wildfire spread was carried out on an ultra-high-resolution modeling domain embedded as a sub-grid in DO3. A grid refinement ratio of 10:1 was adopted, resulting in a fire domain with a horizontal grid spacing of 50 m (mesh size of 1200 × 1200). This spatial resolution was chosen based on the resolution of the terrestrial datasets that are available for its initialization. Specifically, these include terrain elevation data, which is used for deriving slope, and fuels data. The 90 m resolution SRTM (Shuttle Radar Topography Mission) data were used for topography. For the representation of fuels, the 100 m resolution prototype fuel map of Greece, constructed by Giannaros et al. (2019)⁹, was employed.

For the initialization of the WRF-SFIRE numerical simulations, we used the 0.25° x 0.25° spatial resolution and 3 h temporal resolution surface and upper-air ERA5 reanalyses data of the European Centre for Medium-range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF)¹⁰. Model output was stored at 180-, 60-, and 30-minutes interval for the DO1, DO2, and DO3 modeling domains, respectively.

Two numerical experiments were conducted: a) one control simulation with the wind gust parameterization deactivated and b) one simulation with the wind gust parameterization activated. Evaluation of simulations focuses only on fire spread prediction to assess the impact of the wind gust parameterization.

3. Results

According to documentary evidence collected by Lekkas et al. (2018), the Mati wildfire ignited in the region of Ntaou Pentelis at around 17:00 EEST and spreading extremely rapidly, it reached the coast at around 18:30 EEST. Therefore, we focus the evaluation of the WRF-SFIRE simulations at roughly the same period (17:00 to 19:30 EEST).

Figure 1 presents the hourly WRF-SFIRE-simulated fire spread of the Mati wildfire from 17:30 EEST to 19:30 EEST. Unfortunately, the results are discouraging. Focusing on the control

⁷ Tewari, M. et al. (2004) Implementation and verification of the unified NOAA land surface model in the WRF model. In: 20th Conference on Weather Analysis and Forecasting/16th Conference on Numerical Weather Prediction, pp. 11-15.

⁸ Grell, G.A., and Freitas, S.R. (2014) A scale an aerosol aware stochastic convective parameterization for weather and air quality modeling. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* 14, 5233-5250.

⁹ Giannaros, T.M. et al. (2019) IRIS – Rapid response fire spread forecasting system: Development, calibration, and evaluation. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology* 279, 107745.

¹⁰ Hersbach, H. et al. (2020) The ERA5 global reanalysis. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society* 146, 1999-2049.

simulation (Fig. 1, left), it is evident that the model fails to capture the rapid progression of the fire towards the sea. When the wind gust parameterization is activated, fire progression is significantly accelerated (Fig. 1, right). However, the pattern of simulated fire progression is far from realistic. As shown in Fig. 1 (right column), the model reproduces a more southeasterly progression of the fire in the first 1.5 h, while in the following 1 h it erroneously overestimates progression to the north.

Figure 1. WRF-SFIRE-simulated fire spread for the 2018 Mati wildfire without (left) and with (right) the wind gust parameterization. Fire spread prediction is shown from 17:30 EEST (top) to 19:30 EEST (bottom) at hourly intervals.

Examination of the simulated wind field (not shown) reveals that while the wind gust parameterization increases wind speeds by bringing upper-level winds down to the surface, it also yields changes in wind directions that erroneously modify fire progression. This could be due

to the misrepresentation of the direction of upper-level winds in the model that, when brought down to the surface, alter fire progression.

Despite the apparently discouraging results we obtained, the use of wind gusts to drive fire spread in the WRF-SFIRE modeling system does show some potential for improving fire progression predictions. In the future, it is necessary to revisit the developed wind gust parameterization and carefully assess the methods applied to bring down upper-level winds to the surface.

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